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THE CONCEPT AND CONTENT OF INTERCULTURAL DISCOURSE

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the relationship and interdependence of intercultural communication and discursive activity. The main attention is paid to the need to teach intercultural discourse in the light of its national and cultural characteristics; at the same time, the interdisciplinary nature of this phenomenon is taken into account. The substantiation of the choice of interactive methods of teaching a foreign language in order to form the intercultural competence of students as a condition for the implementation of intercultural discourse is given.

Keywords: intercultural communication; discourse; discursive activity; intercultural discourse; participants of discursive interaction; national communication style; intercultural competence.

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ПОНЯТИЕ И СОДЕРЖАНИЕ МЕЖКУЛЬТУРНОГО ДИСКУРСА

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье анализируется взаимосвязь и взаимообусловленность межкультурной коммуникации и дискурсивной деятельности. Основное внимание уделяется необходимости преподавания межкультурного дискурса с учетом его национально-культурных особенностей; при этом учитывается междисциплинарный характер этого явления. Дано обоснование выбора интерактивных методов обучения иностранному языку с целью формирования межкультурной компетенции учащихся как условия реализации межкультурного дискурса.

Ключевые слова: межкультурная коммуникация; дискурс; дискурсивная деятельность; межкультурный дискурс; участники дискурсивного взаимодействия; национальный стиль общения; межкультурная компетенция.

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MADANIYATARO MULOQOT DISKURSI TUSHUNCHASI VA MAZMUNI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada madaniyatlararo muloqot va diskursiv faoliyatning munosabatlari va o'zaro bog'liqligi tahlil qilinadi. Asosiy e'tibor ushu hodisaning fanlararo xususiyatini hisobga olgan holda, madaniyatlararo nutqning milliy-madaniy xususiyatlarini hisobga olgan holda o'rgatish zarurligiga qaratiladi. Madaniyatlararo nutqni amalga oshirish sharti sifatida talabalarning madaniyatlararo kompetentsiyasini shakllantirish uchun chet tilini o'qitishning interfaol usullarini tanlash asoslari keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: madaniyatlararo muloqot; nutq; diskursiv faoliyat; madaniyatlararo nutq; diskursiv o'zaro ta'sir ishtirokchilari; milliy muloqot uslubi; madaniyatlararo kompetentsiya.

In the process of intercultural interaction, a contrast of cultures is manifested, which reflects both the characteristics of communicants and the content of communications, as well as belonging to different cultures. The whole process of human life can be represented in the form of axiological oppositions: useful - harmful, necessary - not necessary, funny - sad, one's own - someone else's, operating at the intracultural and intercultural levels. To analyze intercultural discourse, in our opinion, we should briefly consider the essence of the very concept of "discourse" in modern linguistics due to its multidimensionality and complexity.

In the theory and practice of intercultural communication, particular attention is paid to the question of discourse intercultural relations. Conditional knowledge that underlies an individual's communicative behavior.

The complexity of defining discourse is explained by its interdisciplinary nature. A lot of works are devoted to the study of linguistics, anthropology, literary criticism, ethnography, sociology, sociolinguistics, philosophy, psycholinguistics, cognitive psychology and the question of what speech is, what types of speech and mechanisms for its implementation are.

V.E. Chernyavskaya identifies two main, "working" understandings of what discourse is. On the one hand, discourse is "a specific communicative event recorded in written texts and oral speech, carried out in a specific, cognitively and typologically determined communicative space".

From the same positions, within the framework of the cognitive approach, considers the discourse of E.S. Kubryakova, who interprets it as "a form of using language in real (current) time (on-line), reflecting a certain type of human social activity, is created with the aim of constructing a special world (or its image) using its detailed linguistic description and is generally part the process of communication between people, characterized, like every act of communication, by the participants in communication, the conditions for its implementation and, of course, its goals. Discourse, from the point of view of the researcher, is a speech-thinking process of an interpersonal nature, its characteristics are purposeful, advance planning and goal setting.

Arutyunova N.D. defines discourse as "speech immersed in life". In her opinion, the study of discourse is impossible without taking into account cultural and socio-historical data, without information about why, from what positions and who carried out discursive activity. V.E. Chernyavskaya believes that "discourse in one of its possible understandings denotes a text in close connection with the situational context that determines everything that is essential for the generation of this statement / text, in connection with the system of communicative-pragmatic and cognitive goals of the author, interacting with the recipient. In this sense, the discourse characterizes the communicative process, leading to the formation of a certain structure - the text".

Reflecting on discourse and text, V.E. Chernyavskaya especially emphasizes the fact that discourse does not replace the concept of "text"; text is a kind of formal construction formed as a result of a communicative and mental process (discourse). V. Krasnykh draws attention to the potential possibility of various strategies for constructing text and discourse, which, according to the researcher, are determined, among other things, by the cognitive picture of the world, which ultimately leads to problems in the process of intercultural communication, when "formal "coincidence", the equivalence of verbal units turns into quasi-equivalence at the content level.

Discourse is "a set of thematically related texts: texts combined into a discourse are somehow directed to a common topic. The content (theme) of the discourse is revealed not by a separate text,

but intertextually in the complex interaction of many individual texts. In other words, discourse is seen as "a complex interconnection of many texts operating within the same field of communication." Approaches to the definition of the essence of discourse do not contradict each other, they complement each other.

From all of the above, we can conclude that the discourse is undoubtedly culturally determined. In discourse, as part of the communicative process between people, its national and cultural peculiarity is most clearly manifested, the study of which, on the one hand, makes it possible to identify its nationally specific components, as well as to successfully achieve the set communicative goals in the process of intercultural communication. Turning to the study of the essence of intercultural discourse as such, let us consider the question of the definition of intercultural communication, within which the discursive activity of individuals belonging to different cultural societies takes place.

To refer to intercultural communication today there are many different terms: intercultural or cross-cultural, transcultural, countercultural, intercultural communication. Also, for the current state of the theory and practice of intercultural communication, multiple naming of knowledge areas involved in teaching ICC is also immanent: intercultural consciousness (cross-cultural awareness, cross-cultural perspective), intercultural education (cross-cultural training, intercultural learning, multicultural education), etc. . It should be noted that interest in the issues and research of the IWC as a science is constantly growing, which allows us to conclude that it is significant and solid for modern society.

A review of the literature shows that there are at least two approaches to defining an entity:

- linguistic, relating the processes of intercultural communication by nature to speech activity;
- cultural and anthropological, based on the achievements of many sciences.

Supporters of the linguistic approach (Knapp K., Knapp-Potthoff A., Ladmiral D.R., Lipiansky E., Vereshchagin E.M. and Kostomarov V.G., Maslova

V.A., Ter-Minasova S.G. and others) note the paramount importance of language in the processes of intercultural communication. Communication between representatives of different cultures occurs due to the correct decoding of the language codes characteristic of all members of each of the cultures. Representatives of the cultural-anthropological approach believe that intercultural communication is inevitably accompanied by communicative conflicts due to differences not so much in languages, but due to the different national consciousnesses of the communicants. Despite the differences in interpretations of the essence of the ICC, due to different approaches to its study, one can single out something in common that most researchers of the ICC agree on: intercultural communication is "an interactive process, a process of interaction, the participants of which are representatives of different cultures"; "in the most general form - a direct or indirect exchange of information between representatives of different linguistic cultures."

In his work, L.V. Kulikova considers intercultural discourse as "the interaction between representatives of different cultural and linguistic groups, in which the union of communication partners, expressed implicitly or openly, affects the outcome of the interaction". The communication style factor is one of the main factors in the expression of mixed unions in intercultural dialogue.

Defining the national communicative style as "a stable set of communicative ideas, rules and norms, mediated by culture as a macro-context of communication, which are manifested in the selection of language means, the organization of meaning and the nationally marked communicative behavior of native speakers". L.V. Kulikova emphasizes that in the process of interpersonal intercultural communication, participants demonstrate the standard communicative behavior of a native speaker on the basis of a stable communicative style formed in their linguoculture. The discrepancy between national communication styles often causes communication failures, misunderstandings, and misunderstandings.

For example, in German discourse, long pauses in communication, especially in argumentative ones, have a negative connotation, signaling the uncertainty and, at times, incompetence of the speaker, while such pauses are typical for Finnish discourse and do not have negative connotations.

Based on the prosodic features of national discourses (loudness and tempo of speech, voice timbre, etc.), Americans are perceived in Europe, in particular in England, as too loud. Germans, especially teenagers and young people, are, for example, too loud and unceremonious for Russians for the habit of discussing their affairs in public places without lowering their voices. Representatives of Romance-speaking cultures are characterized by a high rate of speech, while Finns are among the slow-speaking peoples, which gives rise to many stereotypes about them as the biggest silent people in Europe. The non-verbal component of communication is also characterized by national specificity. Thus, in Italian national discourse, gestures accompanying speech specify it, testifying to the sincerity or insincerity of the speaker, his true intentions, etc. In French discourse gestures make speech more lively, conveying the emotions of the speaker.

Thus, the complexity of intercultural discourse lies in the direct interaction of linguistic, semantic, scientific and practical components of individual communicative behavior in the interpretation of all possible meanings. From the point of view of intercultural communication L.V. Kulikova said: "A fundamental component of phonetic individuality in different languages and cultures is the peculiarities of the way countries communicate, which is one of the foundations of the process of personal communication in linguistics."

Donets P.N., analyzing the works of domestic and foreign scientists on the theory and practice of intercultural communication, speaks of two directions in which intercultural discourse is studied: a contrastive-pragmatic direction and an interactive-pragmatic direction. Intercultural discourse within the framework of the contrastive-pragmatic direction is a culturally determined speech acts of low and high levels. Low-level speech acts are the so-called acts of politeness (requests, thanks, questions, apologies, ritualized language formulas and related appeals).

The high or speech macro level includes culturally determined communication strategies to achieve certain goals, fill in pauses, interlocutor's response signals, role behavior, strategies for neutralizing the mistakes made. Within the framework of the interactional-pragmatic direction, the extralinguistic context occupies a central place in the study of intercultural discourse. This context is realized by the participants of intercultural discourse with the help of various markers, such as kinesics, proxemics, prosody, temporal planning (pauses, simultaneous speaking), lexical variation, language formulations. Like L.V. Kulikova, P.N. Donets emphasizes that the cultural mismatch, in this case, extralinguistic contexts leads to intercultural misunderstandings and misunderstandings.

L.S. Suvorova interprets intercultural discourse as one of the varieties of intercultural communication, i.e. "communication within the framework of the interaction of two or more cultures." The communicative behavior of participants in intercultural discourse is aimed at identifying "their" audience and distancing from the "alien". As promising approaches to the study of intercultural discourse, L.S. Suvorova defines a cross-cultural approach and cross-cultural pragmatics. The basis of the cross-cultural approach is the identification a culturally conditioned picture of the world and a deductive description according to the discursive parameters of the main cultural oppositions.

Cross-cultural pragmatics is engaged in a comparative analysis of individual principles that characterize the communicative behavior of an individual as a representative of a certain cultural society and the corresponding cultural scenarios.

Analyzing intercultural discourse, L.S. Suvorova notes that this term is applicable only "to specific situations in which, with equal "social" and "objective" components of the context, there can be different strategically compensatory and actional parameters of intercultural communication. When compiling a classification of situations of intercultural communication, it is necessary to remember the importance of the content of communication itself, "since certain differences in the cognitive base among representatives of different cultures can be partially compensated or deepened depending on the coincidences / inconsistencies in the collective cognitive space associated with referring to a particular subject area, characterizing the content of communication.

So, summing up all the above, we can draw the following conclusions:

- despite the sufficient degree of development of the question of the essence of intercultural discourse, in the modern theory of intercultural communication there is no universal definition of it;

- sharing the points of view of E.S. Kubryakova and L.V. Kulikova, we understand intercultural discourse as a process of mutual contacts between representatives of different cultural and linguistic communities, proceeding in real time, during which the foreignness of communication participants is explicitly or implicitly manifested. Distinctive features of intercultural discourse are, on the one hand, its address correlation, intentionality and goal-setting. On the other hand, the language level of intercultural discourse is inseparable from the cultural correlation of communicative situations and communicative behavior of participants in discursive interaction;

- considering intercultural discourse as a process interpersonal communication in the conditions of intercultural communication, we do not oppose or substitute the concepts of discourse and text, interpreting the latter as the result of a communicative and mental process, i.e. discourse.

As noted above, the mismatch of national communication styles, cultural mismatches lead to intercultural failures, misunderstandings, and misunderstandings. To eliminate the foreignness of participants in intercultural discursive interaction, to understand and analyze the specifics of national discourses, it is necessary to form intercultural competence, which should become an integral part of the language culture of the individual as a whole, as well as an integral part of the professional competence of any specialist who is able to successfully carry out professional activities within the framework of both native, and "foreign" culture.

The rules of courtesy, adopted in the international business and not only the world, dictate certain forms of speech behavior during business negotiations or public speaking. Students' knowledge of the formulas of speech etiquette, lexical units, the ability to stylistically correctly determine the emotionality of statements, as well as the ability to identify differences in intercultural communication, identify the cause of their occurrence and the ability to eliminate such differences will contribute to successful professionally oriented communication in a foreign language in the future.

Thus, the successful professional activity of any specialist in the context of a dialogue of cultures will depend on the ability to understand existing cultural differences, on the ability to identify and resolve them, and, ultimately, on the ability to conduct successful intercultural discursive activities.

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5 ЖИЛД, 4 СОН

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